

THE ILLUSTRATION OF TECHNO – FANTASY IN “ ALIF THE UNSEEN”

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Annotation: The article is about the novel “Alif the Unseen” by G. Willow Wilson and describes the depiction of techno-fantasy used to create the novel. It illustrates the relationships between the Islamic spiritual realities and techno-fantasy genre. It describes Alif’s ideology and its reflection to the world.

Key words: pray, refugee, Alif, style, Jinn, Unseen, technology, Willow Wilson, Arab.

The novel of “Alif the Unseen“ was written by G. Willow Wilson in 2012. Willow Wilson's Alif the Unseen is a thought-provoking blend of techno-thriller and urban fantasy, set in an unnamed Arab emirate. In an unnamed Middle Eastern security state, a young Arab-Indian hacker shields his clients - dissidents, outlaws, Islamists, and other watched groups - from surveillance and tries to stay out of trouble. He goes by Alif - the first letter of the Arabic alphabet, and a convenient handle to hide behind. The aristocratic woman Alif loves has jilted him for a prince chosen by her parents, and his computer has just been breached by the State's electronic security force, putting his clients and his own neck on the line. Then it turns out his lover's new fiancé is the head of State security, and his henchmen come after Alif, driving him underground. When Alif discovers The Thousand and One Days, the secret book of the jinn, which both he and the Hand suspect may unleash a new level of information technology, the stakes are raised and Alif must struggle for life or death, aided by forces seen and unseen. With shades of Neal Stephenson, Neil Gaiman, Philip Pullman, and The Thousand and One Nights, Alif the Unseen is a tour de force debut - a sophisticated melting pot of ideas, philosophy, religion,

technology and spirituality smuggled inside an irresistible page-turner. The novel deals with the idea of revolution and change in the Middle East, despite being written before the Arab Spring. The characters are mostly well done. The standouts are the Imam and Vikram, both wonderfully drawn characters that show a wide range. Dina was maybe a little too close to being the "saint" Alif calls her, but I wouldn't have minded seeing more of her. Alif's computer is attacked by The Hand, a prince who seeks to identify and imprison dissidents. Alif decodes the Alf Yeom and attempts to create a quantum computer. In the City, The Hand's attempt to replicate Alif's quantum computer has failed. The Alf Yeom represents the differences between seen and unseen. In Chapter 0, Reza views the book as the key to jinn magic and believes reading it will bestow mythical abilities upon him. When Alif receives the book in Chapter 3, he begins his journey to the unseen world, something he could not have done without the book. Sakina describes the Alf Yeom as a mindset that humans cannot and were not meant to understand. She adds that Alif's generation interacts differently with information due to the internet, which is similar to the unseen world. Even so, the Alf Yeom is too different from technology for humans to make sense of its stories. When Alif translates the Alf Yeom's metaphors into code, he destroys Sheikh Bilal's computer because magic and technology were not meant to be combined. The Hand's similar failure in subsequent chapters supports this idea. When the Hand tries to code the Alf Yeom, he breaks the internet, and rebellion ensues. Again and again, the Alf Yeom stands as a barrier between the seen and unseen worlds and, thus, between magic and technology.

Alif the Unseen is full of clever, quotable bits and it's a fun Middle Eastern adventure with moderate attempts at profundity. Published just before the Arab Spring ignited, and long before it reached its present tragic outcome, it's an optimistic story using Muslims as characters, good and bad, with hefty doses of magic, adventure, and romance. Where did it fall flat for me? First of all, while not marketed as a Young Adult novel, it is basically written like one. It's clever and well-

written and fun, but light and it's a YA adventure and the protagonists get everything they want in the end in a way that I thought was a little too easy, and some of her messages are delivered with a light anvil. About those messages - I thought G. Willow Wilson was trying just a little too hard to be a proponent of faith (and specifically Islam) without appearing to be. She is not too preachy about it, but even while trying to present a "modern" Islam that has room for diversity and tolerance (a version that sadly exists in no actual Islamic country) in a story for Westerners, it's clear she's reluctant to touch the infallibility of the Quran, say, or feminist critiques of the hijab. I also could not help noticing that the Western convert to Islam in the story, who is only ever referred to as "the convert," is an obvious author stand-in.

"The convert" has taken the hijab, lives in the city of the story, and enthusiastically studies the history and culture of her adopted religion, sort of like a certain Western convert to Islam who now lives in Cairo. The convert is also prone to making arrogant, Western-centric statements in some of the book's most anvilicious moments (presumably Wilson is poking fun at what she perceives as her own failings before she became more enlightened), but where the author really gave it away was when the convert. G. Willow Wilson works magic. Ms. Wilson has not set out to copy JK Rowling's books or anyone else's; she has her own fertile imagination and fanciful narrative style. But as an American convert to Islam, she has an unusual ability to see the best of both worlds. In *Alif the Unseen* she spins her insights into an exuberant fable that has thrills, chills and—even more remarkably—universal appeal.”—Janet Maslin, *The New York Times*. “*Alif the Unseen* is a breezy yet thought-provoking blend of techno-thriller and urban fantasy, set in an unnamed Arab emirate. It will whisk you away to the new vistas of wonder and wisdom excellent modern fairytale. The prose of *Alif the Unseen* is smart and agile; romance and adventure flow easily between Deep Thoughts. Wilson surpasses the early work of Stephenson and Gaiman, with whom comparisons have already

been made. Alif the Unseen will find many fans in both West and East. They will appreciate it for being just the fine story it is and as a seed for potent ideas yet to come. G. Willow Wilson's Alif the Unseen is an embracingly fresh and layered novel that has its faults, but remains entertaining and thought provoking throughout. Not to mention timely, as it deals with the idea of revolution and change in the Middle East, a book that is about the Arab Spring despite being written before the Arab Spring actually took place. Alif the Unseen is set in a nameless "City" in an authoritarian Arab country ruled by an Emir whose security apparatus has long kept the population in check. Included in that apparatus is "one of the most sophisticated digital policing systems in the world," though one that up to now our main hacker protagonist Alif has managed to elude as he lends his considerable computer skills to "anyone who could pay for his protection . . . Islamists, anarchists, secularists—whoever asks."

Alif's ideology is freedom of information, beyond that he seems to believe in little, save that he is in love with an upper-class woman (one well beyond his economic class and his mixed ethnicity). Everything is quickly turned upside down almost immediately in the novel though, as his love tells him she must marry another man, and as Alif begins being tracked by a mysterious State agent with legendary capabilities in tracking down and disappearing hacktivists, a person known only as the Hand of God. The characters are mostly well done. The standouts are the Imam and Vikram, both wonderfully drawn characters that show a wide range. The prince, though he gets much less time, was also a good full character who also added a bit of needed humor. The Convert felt a bit too blunt of a character. Dina was maybe a little too close to being the "saint" Alif calls her, but I wouldn't have minded seeing more of her in a more fully active role; she felt she didn't quite meet her potential. In many ways Alif is the least impressive character, not particularly likable at the start, not particularly compelling at any point really. His blandness is a flaw, but luckily one that is outweighed by the depth of those who surround him, human and

non-human alike. As a bit of a side note, it was also a nice touch that many of these characters are betwixt and between worlds: Alif of mixed ethnicity, the Convert an American turned Muslim and transplanted to the City, Vikram a once-human possessed by a vampire demon. A few other flaws include a somewhat muddled ending, both in terms of plot and simple physical logistics. I really liked the idea of the mystical world mixed with the modern, though I didn't feel it always was executed cleanly or clearly enough. Though one of my favorite exchanges was this one, which takes place in an inn of sorts inside the city of the jinn: Effrit, said the shadow. I'm an effrit. And I've got a two-year-old Dell desktop in the back that's had some kind of virus for ages.

Alif has encountered three strokes of bad luck. The aristocratic woman he loves has jilted him, leaving him with only a mysterious book of fairytales. The state censorship apparatus of the emirate where he lives has broken into his computer, compromising his business providing online freedom for clients across the Islamic world. And now the security police have shown up at his door. But when Alif goes underground, he will encounter a menagerie of mythical creatures and end up on a mad dash through faith, myth, cyberspace, love, and revolution. Alif the Unseen is half political thriller, half contemporary fantasy, taking place in an unnamed City (but basically, Cairo) in an unnamed Middle Eastern country where an autocratic regime closely monitors all Internet activity. Thumbing his nose at the fearsome secret service known only as The Hand, "Alif" (his pseudonym is the first letter of the Arabic alphabet) is a moody teenaged computer prodigy provided anonymous access to any who seek his services. Secularists, Islamists, feminists, pornographers, without discrimination. Alif, despite his computer skills, is just another poor son of immigrants living in the slums. When his rich girlfriend jilts him for an arranged marriage, and he discovers she was basically slumming, he acts like any moody teenaged computer prodigy would - he writes a computer program to monitor her activity on the Internet and erase all mention of him wherever she goes. Yeah, Alif

is kind of a jerk. Then his ex dumps a mysterious book on him, which turns out to be a magical MacGuffin that everyone wants, and his program proves to be very useful for a hyper-monitoring regime like the state, which brings Alif to the attention of the Hand. He becomes a fugitive, on the run and putting everyone he knows and cares about in danger. That's when he runs into djinn. Alif the Unseen is an attempt at Western-style fantasy from a Muslim perspective, and while the author (a Western convert to Islam herself) tries to hang a self-aware lampshade on this, I had mixed reactions to it. G. Willow Wilson is definitely a skilled crafter of words. I have also enjoyed her work on the new Ms. Marvel comic.

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